

INTEGRATED FINITE ELEMENT ENVIRONMENT FOR COMPOSITE PROCESS SIMULATION

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SUMMARY

In this paper the LUSAS **High Precision Moulding (HPM)** integrated finite element environment for composite process simulation is introduced and validated against test components with single and double curvatures. Presented results show dependence on the laminate thickness, radius and in-plane dimensions, these agree well with the experimental data.

Keywords: residual stress, distortion, cure, finite element, composite processing

INTRODUCTION

High performance composites require processing at elevated temperatures, which may lead to the development of residual stresses and distortions. The residual stresses in polymer composites arise primarily from the anisotropic thermal expansion of individual plies, cure shrinkage of the resin and tool-part interaction. Several analytical models have appeared in the literature, which help to understand and estimate the magnitude of distortion, these however are limited to relatively simple geometries usually with single curvatures. Analysis of components with more complex geometries require more sophisticated numerical tools.

Most of the early work was limited to one dimensional simulations. Pusaticiouglu [1] investigated the temperature gradient developed during casting of polyester resin by solving a one-dimensional heat transfer equation using experimentally determined cure kinetics and thermal conductivity. Loos and Springer [2] developed a one-dimensional model to simulate the cure process of a flat plate by solving the governing equations using a finite difference method.

More recent work carried out by Svanberg and Holmberg [3-5], demonstrated that models for residual stress development and shape distortions must account for thermal expansion (different in the glassy and rubbery state), chemical shrinkage due to the cross-linking reaction and stresses that are locked in to the component as the resin vitrifies. A simplified mechanical constitutive model was derived from linear visco-elasticity. The rate dependent behavior was replaced by a path dependence of the state variables: strain, degree of cure, temperature. When compared to a cure simulation using a fully visco-elastic mechanical model the presented model loses a bit of accuracy, however it leads to significant savings in computational time.

Johnston et al. [6] developed an integrated model for the prediction of process-induced stress and distortion of composite structures. A finite element model employing an incremental, instantaneously linear elastic, plane strain formulation was used to analyze major sources of process induced distortions including: thermal strains, resin cure

shrinkage, gradient in temperature and degree of cure, resin flow and mechanical constraints caused by tooling. The interaction between the laminate and the tool was modeled using an elastic “shear layer” with a varying shear modulus depending on the tool-part interface condition.

In this paper the LUSAS High Precision Moulding (HPM) integrated finite element environment for composite process simulation is introduced and validated against test components with single and double curvatures

DESCRIPTION OF THE METHOD

There are two main transitions that can be distinguished during the curing process of a thermosetting resin. The first one is gelation occurring at approximately 30-55 % degree of conversion and the second one is vitrification. Gelation is an irreversible process and corresponds to the formation of a 3-D infinite network of polymer chains. Vitrification occurs once the glass transition temperature reaches the curing temperature and the resin transforms from the rubbery to the glassy, solid state. In the case of neat resin, the development of the resin modulus is explained in Figure 1. Detailed modelling of material stiffness development as well as residual stress build-up requires sophisticated semi-coupled non-linear thermal and structural analyses. The solution method presented here builds on the assumptions of linear visco-elasticity derived by Svanberg and Holmberg [3-5]. During the thermal phase of the analysis temperature and cure gradients are evaluated with possible exotherms which may occur as a result of excess heat generated during cross linking reactions. In the structural part of the analysis, thermal and degree of cure data are read at every time step in order to numerically evaluate corresponding material stiffness and development of residual stresses taking into account phase transitions from liquid to gelled and from gelled to vitrified, glassy state. In the last time step the component is released from the tool and allowed to distort.

Alternatively it is possible to analyse thin laminates using a uniform cure approach. In this approach a uniform temperature/cure distribution across laminate thickness is assumed. This allows the analysis to be conducted in three steps corresponding to cure shrinkage in the rubbery state, cool down from cure temperature and release from the tool. Preliminary results show that for relatively thin laminates ($\approx 5\text{mm}$) difference between uniform cure and semi coupled approach does not exceed 10%.

Fig 1. Development of material properties of epoxy during cure cycle

DEVELOPMENT OF CURE

A novel method of cure data interpolation was implemented and validated against experimental data for the AS4-8552 composite. The method used here is a simplified approach presented earlier by Skordos [7]. The procedure assumes that cure rate at any point during the cure cycle is only a function of cure conversion and temperature. It involves linear interpolation between experimentally determined isothermal cure reaction rates. The method presented here allows the removal of costly and time consuming model fitting. Experimental cure conversion curves used as input for model free kinetics are shown in figure 2. Predicted cure conversion curves show excellent agreement with standard parametric modelling approaches as shown in figure 3

Fig.2 Experimental cure conversion curves as input for model free kinetics

Fig.3 Comparison between model kinetics and interpolated cure conversion curves for random temperature cycle.

VALIDATION CASES

LUSAS HPM was validated against a series of composite components with increasing complexity, starting from C-shaped laminates, through U-channels to components of doubly curved geometry.

C-SHAPES

HPM analysis of 4 C-shaped laminates with a cross-ply stacking sequence has been performed following the continuous development of material properties as well as by the uniform cure approach. All specimens were manufactured on the inside of a cylindrical tooling as a part of the COMPAVS program and are described in more detail in [8]. The material used was unidirectional AS4-8552 composite with a fiber volume fraction of 57%. Specimens were cured following the Manufacturers Recommended Cure Cycle(MRCC). The MRCC consists of a first ramp of 2 °C/min up to 120 °C and a first hold at 120 °C for 60 min, a second ramp of 2 °C/min up to 180 °C and a second hold at 180 °C for 120 min. The thickness was varied from 1 to 4 mm and the outside (tooling) radius was equal to 25mm. Cross ply symmetric $[90/0]_{ns}$ was used with the 90 degree direction following the curvature of the model.

The geometry of the numerical model was recreated within LUSAS Modeller and meshed using structural and thermal layered composite elements. Radial boundary conditions were applied on the outside surface to represent the tooling surface. Upon cool-down radial boundary conditions were removed and the component was allowed to distort. Schematic representation of the analysed component is shown in figure 4.

Fig. 4 Geometry and mesh of the C-shaped laminates. Radial boundary conditions were applied on the tooling surface

The method of calculating the spring-in angle is the same as used by Ersoy et al. [9] The spring-in was calculated by measuring the change in the external diameter and converting it to angular change using equation [1]

$$\Delta\theta = \frac{\pi}{2} \left(\frac{r}{r'} - 1 \right) \quad (1)$$

where r is the radius of the tool at the curing temperature and r' is the radius of the sample measured at room temperature.

Fig 5. Correlation between experimental and LUSAS FE model for laminates of different thickness

It is shown in figure 5 that with increase in laminate thickness spring-in decreases. A small difference in predicted spring-in was observed between uniform cure and continuous methods. This difference was attributed to sharp changes in material stiffness in the uniform cure approach whereas in the continuous analysis phase transitions are more gradual.

SPAR WITH PLY DROPS

U-shaped specimens with ply drops were manufactured by Bombardier Aerospace Belfast and analysed within the LUSAS HPM environment as a part of the WILMA project. The component was manufactured by Resin Transfer Infusion (RTI) from HTA reinforcement and Hexcel RTM6 resin with a fibre volume fraction of 60%. The component geometry, shown in figure 6 was provided by Bombardier Aerospace Belfast in IGES format and imported into LUSAS Modeller. The thickness of the

component is equal to 6.28mm except for two ply build-up regions where it increases to 12.58 mm. LUSAS structural and thermal layered composite elements were used throughout the model. Five elements were used around the corner and two elements were assigned in the thickness direction as shown in figure 6.

Fig 6 . Geometry of the spar. LUSAS finite element mesh of the spar

The laminate stacking sequence was provided in XML format and imported into the LUSAS HPM environment. The applied cure cycle starts at 80 degrees, which is the temperature of the preheated resin. After injection the resin reaches the tooling temperature of 120°C and after a period of 60 min the temperature is increased to 180°C at 1°C/min. After 120 min at 180°C the temperature is reduced to 20 °C over a period of 3 hours. Normal boundary conditions were assigned on the outside of the laminate to represent tooling. These supports were removed after completion of cure and the laminate was allowed to distort.

Spring-in is defined as the change in the angle between each flange of the spar and the web. Predicted and experimentally measured spring-in was determined using an equivalent method. The angle between the flange and the web was taken as being the angle between lines drawn from the end of each flange to the end of the radius, figure 7, to take account of the flange distortion (bowing). Comparison between experimental and numerical results is shown in figure 8. The predicted spring-in along the length of the spar is generally in very good agreement with measured results. In the areas of ply build-ups predicted spring-in angle decreases. This correlates well with the results presented earlier for C-shaped laminates where spring-in also decreased with increasing laminate thickness.

Figure 7. Schematic representation of the spring-in angle in laminates

Figure 8. Comparison between experimental data and numerical prediction for composite spar

HEAT OF REACTION

During curing of the thermosetting composites the resin undergoes cross-linking reactions which lead to an increase of material density and reduction in volume. The cross linking reaction is highly exothermic and in some cases, where heat cannot escape fast enough from the curing component, can lead to damage of the entire part. Exothermic temperature rise is proportional to reaction rate. The LUSAS Resin Cure model allows for accurate prediction of exothermic reaction and accordingly allows tailoring of the cure cycle to avoid component damage. The following example, figure 9, illustrates curing process of a composite spar demonstrator. The component under investigation was 3.5 m long. The thickness was 50 mm and was uniform along the component length. The material used was RTM6 resin and HTS fibers with the volume fraction of 60 %. The laminate was manufactured on composite tooling following Bombardier Aerospace Belfast's RTI process. LUSAS structural and thermal layered composite elements were used throughout the model.

Fig.9 Geometry and mesh of the 3.5 m RTI spar

The comparison between the measured and predicted temperature profile is shown in figure 10. It can be seen that the start and finish of the exothermic reaction is predicted very accurately. The absolute amplitude of the exotherm is higher in the model than in the test. This can be attributed to inaccuracies in the application of thermal boundary conditions as well as the location of the sampling point.

During the manufacturing process the temperature was measured on the tooling whereas in the finite element model the tooling was replaced by thermal boundary conditions and the temperature was sampled directly on the composite component. It is believed that after including tooling in the FE model a much better match could be obtained.

Fig.10 Comparison between measured and predicted temperature history for the 50mm thick spar

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper the LUSAS High Precision Moulding (HPM) integrated finite element environment for composite process simulation has been introduced and validated against test components with single and double curvatures. A novel method of cure data interpolation was implemented and validated against experimental data for the AS4-8552 composite. Predicted cure conversion curves show excellent agreement with a standard parametric modelling approach. It was observed that in C-shaped laminates an increase in the laminate thickness results in a decrease in spring-in angle. A similar observation was made on the spar with ply build-ups where spring-in was also observed to decrease in thicker regions. A small difference in predicted spring-in was observed between uniform cure and continuous methods. This difference was attributed to sharp changes in material stiffness in the uniform cure approach whereas in the continuous analysis phase transitions are more gradual.

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